

Prediction of Vortex Interference on a Canard Controlled Missile

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Abstract

The ability of a component build-up aerodynamic prediction program (Missile Datcom) to predict vortex interference effects is assessed. A brief discussion of the simple vortex models used in the program is presented. Comparisons are made with test data from a canard controlled missile. Very good agreement is found at low angles of attack, even for cross-coupling effects (e.g., yaw due to roll command). At moderate angles of attack, deficiencies in the vortex model degrade the accuracy.

Nomenclature

C_l	Rolling moment coefficient, $l/q_\infty S d$
C_m	Pitching moment coefficient, $M/q_\infty S d$
C_N	Normal force coefficient, $N/q_\infty S$ (aeroballistic axis system)
C_N'	Normal force coefficient, $N/q_\infty S$ (fin axis system)
C_n	Yawing moment coefficient, $n/q_\infty S d$
d	Body diameter, 2.50 in
K_B	Fin-body carryover factor
K_F	Body-fin carryover factor
k_F	Body-fin incidence factor
K_ϕ	Roll angle correction factor
M	Free stream Mach number
q_∞	Free stream dynamic pressure, lb/ft ²
S	Body base area, 4.9088 in ²
α	Total angle-of-attack (fig 1)
α_b	Body axis angle-of-attack (fig 1)
β_b	Body axis sideslip angle (fig 1)
δ	Fin deflection angle
Λ	Adjacent fin interference factor
ϕ	Aerodynamic roll angle

Introduction

One of the key decisions to be made in the missile design process is the means for controlling the trajectory. A satisfactory, robust, autopilot design requires good knowledge of the aerodynamic response due to control deflection. Three types of aerodynamic controllers have been successfully used. They are categorized as canard (forward of the center of gravity), wing (on or near the center of gravity), and tail (aft of the center of gravity) controls. There are inherent advantages and disadvantages with each type of controller. Advantages for canard control include improved

responses due to pitch and yaw commands, since the commanded force is in the direction of the desired motion, and improved packaging of the guidance system. Placement of the control actuators forward of the propulsion system is more desirable than wrapping them around the rocket nozzle, as is required with tail controlled missiles.

The primary disadvantage of a canard controlled missile is the highly nonlinear aerodynamic behavior which arises from a control deflection at low angles of attack. This behavior is due to interactions between the canard vortices and the tail fins. With a roll command, it is common to find that the moment generated is the opposite of the commanded moment (i.e., roll reversal).

Widely differing techniques for estimating these interference effects have been advocated. An empirical technique, suitable for hand calculations, is given by Herring [1]. Computerized methods of varying degrees of sophistication have been developed. Nielsen, Hensch, and Smith [2] developed a semi-empirical technique valid for certain classes of missile geometries. A method based on slender body potential theory is given by Gur et al [3]. A paneling method based on supersonic linear theory has been developed by Dillenius and Nielsen [4].

In the design environment, proper matching of the prediction method to the specific need in terms of accuracy, speed, and cost is essential. An aerodynamic prediction program oriented towards the conceptual/preliminary design environment, Missile Datcom, has recently been developed. It is a compilation of prediction methods taken from many sources. Ease of set-up, rapid turnaround time, and clarity of output were all driving factors during the program development. This paper will assess the ability of Missile Datcom to predict the flow nonlinearities which are encountered by canard controlled missiles.

Missile Datcom

Background

The first comprehensive set of aerodynamic stability and control prediction methods, the USAF Datcom [5], was published in 1960. It has been republished several times since then. Many organizations applied the aircraft based Datcom methods to missile configurations with mixed

success. A study completed in 1981 concluded that a separate Missile Datcom should be developed [6]. Development of the Missile Datcom began in 1981, and it has continued to the present time. Several papers documenting its progress and interim capabilities have been published [7-9]. A brief review of the methodology pertinent to the present analysis will be presented.

All "internal" calculations of Missile Datcom are performed in the total angle of attack - aerodynamic roll coordinate system. This system is commonly known as the "aeroballistic axis system" (figure 1). Body axis angle of attack and sideslip angle are transformed to total angle of attack and roll angle through the following relations:

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1}[(\tan \alpha_b)^2 + (\tan \beta_b)^2]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$\phi = \tan^{-1}[\tan \beta_b / \tan \alpha_b] \quad (2)$$

This axis system is also used in the following discussion.

Equivalent Angle-of-Attack Concept

Missile Datcom uses a "component build-up" approach to determine the total forces and moments on a configuration. Using this technique, estimates are made for the isolated body and fin panels. Interference effects are then applied, and the results are summed to give the overall aerodynamics. The interference effects are based on the "equivalent angle-of-attack" concept developed by Hemsch and Nielsen [10]. This concept is a nonlinear extension of the method developed by Pitts, Nielsen, and Kaattari [11]. The equivalent angle-of-attack is defined as that angle-of-attack for an isolated fin (no interference effects) which results in a force normal to the fin identical to the one generated in the actual missile flow field. The equivalent angle-of-attack is found by a two-step procedure. First, the equivalent angle-of-attack for a non-deflected fin is found:

$$\tan \alpha_{eq_{\delta=0}} = K_F \tan \alpha \cos \phi + F K_\phi \tan \alpha \sin \alpha \sin \phi \cos \phi + \tan \Delta \alpha_{vortices} \quad (3)$$

The first two terms on the right of equation (3) represent the effects of body upwash and bank angle respectively. The last term includes the effects of both body vorticity and vorticity from all upstream fins. The effects of deflection and interference from adjacent fins in the set are then added, to give the total equivalent angle-of-attack:

$$\tan \alpha_{eq_\delta} = k_F \left[\tan(\alpha_{eq_{\delta=0}} + \delta) - \tan \alpha_{eq_{\delta=0}} \right] + \sum_{j=2}^n (\Lambda_j \delta_j) + \tan \alpha_{eq_{\delta=0}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{so } \alpha_{eq_\delta} = \tan^{-1}(\tan \alpha_{eq_\delta}) \quad (5)$$

Each individual panel has its own associated

equivalent angle-of-attack. In Missile Datcom, computed values for alpha-equivalent are used to interpolate the predicted fin-alone normal-force and axial-force characteristics. These calculations are necessarily carried out in a local coordinate system attached to the fin in question. Thus, the "local" forces must be resolved into the aeroballistic axis system:

$$C_{N_F} = C_{N'_F} \cos \delta \sin \phi \quad (6)$$

This result represents, in the aeroballistic axis system, the total force on a single fin in the presence of the body. To obtain the total configuration normal force, the carryover from the fins onto the body and the isolated body results are added to the sum of the individual fin results:

$$C_N = C_{N_B} + \sum_{sets} [(1+K_B/K_F) \sum_{fins} C_{N'_F}] \quad (7)$$

For missiles with multiple fin sets (up to four sets are permitted), the calculation must proceed from front to back. This ensures that the normal force on each fin reflects the alpha-equivalent contribution of all upstream vortices. Moment coefficients are computed directly from the forces and computed center-of-pressure locations.

Vortex Modeling

Missile Datcom uses a very simple model for both body and fin vortices and their effects on downstream fins (figure 2). More sophisticated models are available, but they are computationally intensive, which results in increases in both cost and turnaround time. Improved vortex models are now being implemented into Missile Datcom as options to allow for improved predictions where cost and speed are not driving factors.

Body Vortices

At low angles of attack (roughly 5 degrees), the flow on the leeside of a body separates, forming a sheet of vorticity. This sheet eventually rolls up into a symmetrical vortex pair, affecting the load distribution on the aft portion of the body and on fins downstream of the separation point. Missile Datcom represents these vortices as a pair of concentrated vortex filaments. The separation point, downstream trajectory, and strength of these filaments is determined using empirical charts derived by Hemsch et al [12]. These charts are based on test data of differing nose shapes on a cylindrical afterbody, at both subsonic and supersonic conditions. In addition to the nose vortices discussed above, missiles with long boattails can shed additional vortices at moderate angles of attack. These vortices are not modeled in Missile Datcom.

Fin Vortices

A fin at angle of attack sheds a vortex sheet which rolls up into a concentrated vortex down-

stream. About three root chords downstream from the trailing edge, the roll-up process is complete, and the vortex can be modeled as a single vortex filament. Investigators have modeled this process using multiple filaments downstream, but a single vortex model correlates well with experimental data [3,11]. A single vortex is also the simplest to treat. Missile Datcom assumes a fully rolled up vortex filament is shed from the fin trailing edge. This vortex is not shed from the tip, but from the centroid of the fin load distribution, as determined from charts based on vortex lattice theory. The vortex is assumed to track downstream along the velocity vector. Stoy and Vukelich [13] studied alternate tracking schemes using a single vortex filament and concluded that a linear track along the velocity vector was the most accurate.

Vortex Interactions

Mutual interactions between body and fin vortices as they move downstream are not treated in Missile Datcom. Missile Datcom computes the load on downstream fins by estimating the equivalent angle-of-attack increment due to the vortices. This analysis is carried out in the crossflow plane. A series of charts presented by Pitts et al [11] give interference factors for given a vortex position and strength in the crossflow plane of a fin. For each vortex and fin orientation, Missile Datcom transforms this interference factor into an equivalent angle-of-attack. These equivalent angles-of-attack are summed to give the overall fin alpha-equivalent due to vortices.

Vortices can track to positions which intersect downstream fins. As reported by Gur et al [3], anomalous predictions result if this occurs. Missile Datcom maintains a minimum distance between vortices and fins, based on the work of Spreiter and Sacks [14]. In the crossflow plane of the tail, it is possible for a vortex from a windward fin to track to a position inside or above the body at high angles of attack. If either of these occurs, Missile Datcom sets the vortex strength to zero. This is in violation of the Helmholtz law of vorticity, but is physically realistic, in that the vortex is absorbed by the boundary layer along the body. The Helmholtz law is predicated on a potential flow.

Experimental Configuration

There is a wealth of experimental data available on almost all types of missiles, including canard controlled missiles. The configuration chosen for analysis in this paper (figure 3) was tested by Blair in the NASA Langley Unitary Plan Wind Tunnel [15,16]. Two sets of fins (four fins each) were mounted on the body. The missile was tested with the forward (canard) fins in the plus (+) orientation and the aft fins in either the (+) or (x) orientation. Testing was also conducted with the tail fins off. The bulk of the data to be presented will be at a Mach number of 1.7, where the interference effects are most pronounced.

Data Comparisons

Pitch Command

The normal force comparison for the plus-tail configuration is shown in figure 4. Excellent agreement is found at all angles of attack. Pitching moment predictions for the plus tail are given in figure 5 for zero and five degrees of canard deflection. Outstanding agreement is evident at all angles of attack. The slight break in slope at two degrees angle of attack for the five degree canard deflection is due to the vortex from the canard crossing over to the top of the tail fin. Predictions of the x-tail pitching moment characteristics are presented in figure 6. Very good agreement is found up to ten degrees angle of attack; at higher angles, the moment is under-predicted. However, the difference between the two curves remains well predicted. For the x-tail, the slope break due to the canard vortex passing over the tail fin occurs at six degrees angle of attack. This is greater than for the plus-tail since the x-tail fins are mounted at a higher vertical location.

Roll Command

Roll commands were generated by deflecting the left horizontal canard panel five degrees (trailing edge down) and the right horizontal canard panel five degrees (trailing edge up). Hence, a positive rolling moment was commanded. As seen in figure 7, the tail-off rolling moment predictions are high by about 20-30% across the angle of attack range. This is probably due to the simplicity of the method used for estimating fin lateral center of pressure. The method is a function of the fin-span to body-diameter ratio only, and gives values which only vary from 0.416 to 0.424 of the fin span. An improved method is now being developed [17], which will include the effects of fin planform, Mach number, and angle of attack.

For the plus-tail configuration, the addition of the tails results in a change in sign of the resultant rolling moment (roll reversal). This is due to the loads induced on the tail fins by the vortices from the canards. The induced effect decreases above ten degrees angle of attack, but the prediction remains largely unchanged. This may be due to mutual interaction among the vortices, which Missile Datcom ignores. For the x-tail (figure 8), roll reversal is also evident at low angles of attack. The induced effect is highest in the 6-8 degree alpha range, due to the vortices passing over the upper tail fins. Missile Datcom does pick up this effect, but again misses the behavior above ten degrees angle of attack.

A sketch of the predicted flow field is given in figure 9. Shown are the locations and strengths of the canard vortices relative to the plus-tail planform at three angles of attack. An asymmetry in vortex strength is evident as the angle of attack increases. This arises from the differential

deflection, in that (neglecting interference effects) the left canard fin "sees" an angle of attack of $(\alpha + 5)$, while the right fin "sees" an angle of attack of $(\alpha - 5)$. Hence the normal force and vortex strength for the left fin are greater than for the right fin. The induced angles of attack at the tail fins (roughly 1.5 degrees) are small relative to the five degree control deflection. However, four fins contribute to the adverse rolling moment, compared to only two contributing to the commanded moment. In addition, the area of a tail fin is roughly three times the canard fin area, so the induced rolling moment is greater than the commanded moment, and roll reversal occurs.

The variation in the rolling moment coefficient with Mach number for the plus-tail is presented in figure 10. The trend in the test data is very well predicted (tail-off data were not available vs Mach number). As the Mach number increases, the tail off moment decreases due to a reduction in the lift curve slope (and hence roll effectiveness) of the canard. This reduction decreases the strength of the canard trailing vortex, so the interference effect (tail-on minus tail-off) also decreases. In general, interference effects will reduce with increasing supersonic Mach number, due to a reduction in the strength of the canard vortices.

Predictions of yawing moment due to a roll command are presented in figures 11-12. Missile Datcom predicts the tail-off values to be zero at all angles of attack, while the data show small positive yawing moments at the higher angles of attack. This may be due to interactions between the canard and body vortices. When the tails are added, Missile Datcom predicts a small positive induced yawing moment with increasing angle of attack. This levels off above ten degrees angle of attack. These moments are caused by the difference in the canard vortex strengths, which increase with angle of attack. This strength differential induces positive side forces on the upper tail fins, which give small yawing moments. The plus-tail data show almost no effect except at the higher angles of attack. The x-tail data show a trend in qualitative agreement with the prediction.

Yaw Command

Yaw commands were generated by deflecting of the top and bottom canard panels ten degrees each (trailing edge right). Thus, a negative yawing moment was commanded. Missile Datcom does an excellent job of predicting the tail-off yawing moment (figures 13-14). With the plus-tail, a large increase in yawing moment is induced near zero angle of attack. This rapidly diminishes with alpha and eventually results in a reduced overall yawing moment. Missile Datcom correctly predicts the magnitude of the induced effect at up to eight degrees alpha. Above this, the prediction asymptotically approaches the tail off value, since only the upper canard vortex contributes to the yawing moment. The trend in the data at higher angles of attack is probably due to interactions

between the vortices, which Missile Datcom ignores. The correlations for the x-tail configuration are identical, except that the magnitude of the induced effects is smaller. This is due to the increased distance between the canard vortices and the tail fins.

Rolling moment due to yaw command comparisons are presented in figures 15-16. As expected, the tail-off values are zero across the angle of attack range. When the tails are added, positive rolling moments are induced which increase with angle of attack, and peak at an angle of attack of about eight to ten degrees. This is due to the upward movement of the canard vortices in the crossflow plane of the tail. As the angle of attack increases, the windward canard vortex will impinge on the body, leaving only the leeward vortex. This vortex will lose influence as it moves further from the body. As a result, a peak in rolling moment will occur, which will diminish with increasing alpha. Missile Datcom correctly predicts the variation in rolling moment up to the peak, but misses the variation above the peak. As before, this is probably due to interactions among the vortices, which are ignored by Missile Datcom.

Design Alternatives

The desirability of canard control for missiles has led investigators to seek means for minimizing the adverse induced effects. The simplest approach is to reduce the span of the tail fin [18]. This decreases the area of the tail fin so that the adverse induced rolling moment is lessened. Missile Datcom was used to estimate the magnitude of this effect for a 33% and 67% nominal fin span. As seen in figure 17, the induced effects are dramatically reduced, and the roll reversal disappears for the 33% nominal span case. Simply reducing the span can have a significant drawback in that it changes the longitudinal stability and normal force characteristics. An alternate approach could be to reduce the tail fin span, but increase its chord, such that the static margin (or normal force) is held constant. This would increase the distance between the canard vortex and tail fin, reducing the equivalent angle of attack induced by the vortex. Maintaining a constant static margin may be difficult; however, as the fin aspect ratio and the effective moment arm would both be reduced.

A proposal which nearly eliminates the interference effects on the tail fins is the use of a free rolling tail [15]. With a free rolling tail, the tail fins impart no adverse rolling moment (neglecting friction) to the body. The normal force and longitudinal stability characteristics remain unchanged with a tail which is free to roll.

Conclusions

An aerodynamic prediction program intended for preliminary design, Missile Datcom, has been developed. To minimize the cost and turnaround

time associated with its use, very simple vortex models are used in combination with the equivalent angle-of-attack concept. The ability of Missile Datcom to predict the characteristics of a canard controlled missile, where vortex interference effects are dominant, was assessed. The following conclusions are drawn:

(a) The fin lateral center of pressure method may be inadequate for preliminary design. An improved method is now being implemented.

(b) The vortex models in Missile Datcom are adequate for assessing interference effects at low angles of attack. Roll reversal, a common problem with canard controlled missiles, was accurately predicted by Missile Datcom.

(c) At moderate angles of attack (roughly ten degrees) and above, vortex interactions ignored by Missile Datcom degrade accuracy.

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Figure 1 Axis System Nomenclature

Figure 2 Vortex Model

Figure 3 Model Dimensions

Figure 4 Normal Force Correlation

Plus Tail M = 1.7

Figure 5 Pitching Moment Correlation

Pitch Command Plus Tail M = 1.7

Figure 6 Pitch Moment Correlation

Pitch Command X Tail M = 1.7

Figure 7 Rolling Moment Correlation

Roll Command Plus Tail M = 1.7

Figure 10 Rolling Moment Correlation

Alpha = 0.0 Delta = 5.0

Figure 8 Rolling Moment Correlation

Roll Command X Tail M = 1.7

Figure 11 Yawing Moment Correlation

Roll Command Plus Tail M = 1.7

Figure 9 Canard Vortex Positions

Predicted Location at Tail Fins

Γ = NONDIMENSIONAL VORTEX STRENGTH
 α = ANGLE OF ATTACK

Figure 12 Yawing Moment Correlation

Roll Command X Tail M = 1.7

Figure 13 Yawing Moment Correlation

Yaw Command Plus Tail M = 1.7

Figure 16 Rolling Moment Correlation

Yaw Command X Tail M = 1.7

Figure 14 Yawing Moment Correlation

Yaw Command X Tail M = 1.7

Figure 17 Effect Of Reduced Tail Fin Span

Roll Command Plus Tail M = 1.7

Figure 15 Rolling Moment Correlation

Yaw Command Plus Tail M = 1.7

